

**EFFECTS OF LESSON ORGANIZATION IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE
CLASSES IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS USING INTERACTIVE
METHODS**

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Annotation: Today, the younger generation is increasingly interested in learning foreign languages. Therefore, teaching a foreign language, including English, in secondary schools requires the use of interactive methods in the classroom. This article focuses on the effectiveness of organizing lessons using interactive methods in English classes in secondary schools.

Keywords: method, interactive method, information and communication technologies, interactivity.

Significant work is being done in our country to form an information society, to introduce the most advanced information and communication technologies in all areas. In particular, the capabilities of interactive services in this process are highly valued. The Uzbek dictionary defines the term "interactive" as based on the reception or transmission of information over a computer network. Wikipedia, on the other hand, evaluates interactivity as a concept that reveals the nature and extent of interactions between objects and is said to be used in information theory, computer science and programming, telecommunications systems, sociology, industrial design, and more. In short, interactivity is a system of organizing the system to achieve a specific goal by facilitating the exchange of information between parts of the system. The interactive method is aimed at activating the acquisition of knowledge and developing personal qualities of students by increasing the activity between students and the teacher in the educational process. Using interactive

methods can help increase lesson effectiveness. The main criteria for interactive education are: informal discussions, the ability to freely express and express the learning material, a small number of lectures, but a large number of seminars, opportunities for students to take the initiative, small group, large group, assignment to work as a class team, written work and other methods, which are of particular importance in increasing the effectiveness of educational work.

One of the main directions in improving teaching methods today is the introduction of interactive teaching and learning methods. All science teachers are increasingly using interactive methods in their teaching. As a result of using interactive methods, students develop the skills of independent thinking, analysis, drawing conclusions, expressing their opinions, defending them on the basis of them, healthy communication, discussion, debate. In the process of interactive learning, the lesson is based on the interaction of students.

Modern interactive methods in foreign language teaching methods have been developed by scientists and have proven to be more effective than traditional methods. Interactive methods significantly increase the knowledge potential of the learning process compared to traditional methods. Because in interactive methods, the student thinks independently and works in partnership with the teacher. When teaching a foreign language with the help of modern technologies, the student plans the lesson process, engages in it on the basis of the curriculum set by him, the teaching methods are chosen jointly by the student and the teacher. participate in the discussion of the study material. Students help each other. In the late twentieth and early twenty-first centuries, the term "interactive" methods of education is widely used in pedagogical literature. We will try to explain the meaning of this phrase. "Inter" is used in the extreme sense. Interactive means a very active learning method. This group of methods allows students to think independently, be creative, and be interested in the essence of the topic. It is more effective than traditional methods of teaching, such as interactive methods of explanation, demonstration and

use of tools, which are an important factor in the formation of students as individuals, the development of personal abilities, creative independence.

It should be noted that interactive teaching methods in Uzbekistan since ancient times in the educational process in the form of discussion, debate, negotiation, observation, analysis, consultation, poetry reading, reading in the dialogue between teacher and students and between students and students. used. These methods helped to develop students' independent thinking and perfection by developing their speech, thinking, reasoning, intelligence, talent, and intelligence.

Literatures:

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